

Pre-Pottery Neolithic Gre Filla

By Özlem EKİNBAŞ CAN, Kocaeli University

Entry tags: Religious Group, Neolithic, Ritual centre, Religious Place, North Mesopotamia

Gre Filla, covering an area of 0.5 ha and ca.7-8 in height, is located on the eastern bank of the Ambar stream and is in the south of the modern Ambar village near the Kocaköy district of Diyarbakır province. Salvage excavations at Gre Filla, carried out within the Ambar Dam Project brought out a Pre-Pottery Neolithic (PPN) settlement, located on the northern border of the alluvial plain formed by the tributaries of the Upper Tigris valley. The main settlement period is the Pre-Pottery Neolithic, presenting a sequence dating to 9300-7500 cal. BC. The Pottery Neolithic period is represented only by potsherds; the architecture seems to have been destroyed by the Late Roman and Medieval periods graves. Salvage excavations conducted in two different areas, the north, and the south operations revealed that the settlement layout in the northern operation is marked by three oval subterranean structures, separated by ca. 9-10 m from each other. Each oval structure is surrounded by quadrangular buildings separated by narrow paths connecting them. The grouping of quadrangular structures around each oval structure left the impression of subgroups, each making use of the subterranean structure in the middle of their residential circle. Likewise, in the southern operation were uncovered another oval structure and several quadrangular buildings. Taking into account the radiocarbon dates and the undisturbed stratigraphic position of the oval and quadrangular buildings, it seems clear that both building plan types had been used simultaneously. The oval buildings are ca. 7.5 × 10 m in dimension, each equipped with four pillars constructed of limestone and mud mortar. The walls, renewed multiple times, were not always fully placed on top of one another, causing the appearance of intertwined walls. Several large rooms were furnished with 1-4 stone bases for wooden posts to support the roof. Some buildings have mud plaster on the walls. Preliminary assessment of faunal and micro-floral remains, though they are still under study, shows that the inhabitants of Gre Filla consumed primarily sheep, goat, cattle, wild boar, deer, rodents, rabbit and birds and lentils, hackberry, grape, etc in their subsistence economy. So far, a few human remains, some of which were furnished with grave goods, were unearthed. Single-burial was practiced and deceased people were interred mostly under the floor or under and/or next to the walls associated with the structures in a flexed position (hocker). There could not be found any special burial facilities at the site.

Date Range: 9300 BCE - 7500 BCE

Region: Diyarbakır Region

Region tags: Turkey, Gre Filla

This region encompasses the Upper Tigris Basin including Diyarbakır province

Status of Participants:

✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

- Water source
- Body of water (as distinct from source)

Notes: The site is ca.90 m away from the Ambar Stream, which is a tributary of the Tigris River.

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Since the fieldwork has been terminated after the 2022 season, it is unknown whether these types of structures were present in the unexcavated area.

↳ One single feature

–Other [specify]: No

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Notes: At the site, it was unearthed both oval and quadrangular structures that were in use contemporarily.

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Since the excavation region is not fully investigated, it is unclear, at the time being, to assume the presence of a larger place

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Other [specify]: The presence of benches where 26 people can sit in some buildings and ritual objects in the same area make these structures communal. Yet, it is also possible that a particular group or person worshipped alone within these structures.

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

↳ In antiquity

– More than once

Notes: Traces of reconstruction activities in several buildings can be followed more than twice.

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: The presence of a human statue in public buildings is associated with ancestor worship (-----)

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Field doesn't know

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Ökse, A. T. (2020). Yukarı Dicle Havzası–Ambar Çayı Vadisi Yerleşim Tarihi. Olba, 28 (XXVIII), 1-34.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– Field doesn't know

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– Field doesn't know

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

↳ Type of excavation:

– Pre-modern

↳ Years of excavation:

–Year range: Since 2018

↳ Name of excavation

–Official or descriptive name: Ambar Dam Salvage Excavations (Gre Filla, Kendale Hecala and Ambar Höyük)

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

↳ Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Notes: Ambar Höyük is only 100 meters (as the crow flies) in the north of Gre Filla while Kendale Hecala is 700 m (as the crow flies) situated in the southeast of Gre Filla

↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Field doesn't know

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– Field doesn't know

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– I don't know

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Field doesn't know

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– No

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: No

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Ökse, A. T. (2020). Yukarı Dicle Havzası-Ambar Çayı Vadisi Yerleşim Tarihi. Olba, 28 (XXVIII), 1-34.

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Pre-modern

Years of excavation:

– Year range: Since 2018

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Ambar Dam Salvage Excavations (Gre Filla, Kendale Hecala and Ambar Höyük)

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

- Water source
- Body of water (as distinct from source)

Notes: The site is ca.90 m away from the Ambar Stream, which is a tributary of the Tigris River.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Notes: Ambar Höyük is only 100 meters (as the crow flies) in the north of Gre Filla while Kendale Hecala is 700 m (as the crow flies) situated in the southeast of Gre Filla

Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– Field doesn't know

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Since the fieldwork has been terminated after the 2022 season, it is unknown whether these types of structures were present in the unexcavated area.

↳ One single feature

–Other [specify]: No

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Notes: At the site, it was unearthed both oval and quadrangular structures that were in use contemporarily.

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Since the excavation region is not fully investigated, it is unclear, at the time being, to assume the presence of a larger place

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

–Other [specify]: The presence of benches where 26 people can sit in some buildings and ritual objects in the same area make these structures communal. Yet, it is also possible that a particular group or person worshipped alone within these structures.

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

↳ In antiquity

– More than once

Notes: Traces of reconstruction activities in several buildings can be followed more than twice.

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: The presence of a human statue in public buildings is associated with ancestor worship (-----)

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Field doesn't know

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– Field doesn't know

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Field doesn't know

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– I don't know

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Field doesn't know

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– No

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: No

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

Notes: On two of the walls of stone pillars situated in the center of the structure were found red plaster partially. As the plaster partly survived, it is obscure if there were any decorative elements on them.

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction,

etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

↳ Statues of humans:

– Yes

Notes: A human statue of approximately 38,5 cm in height inside Public Building 15 is associated with the ancestor cult (Schmandt-Besserrat, 2013: 329).

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

Notes: The human face was carved in relief on the 2 altars in Public Building 15.

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– No

↳ Other type of decoration:

–Yes [specify]: On the floor of one of the Public Building was found terrazzo floor.

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:
– No

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:
– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:
– Field doesn't know

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)
– Yes
Notes: Stylized eye detail is indicated on some zoomorphic pestles.

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)
– Yes
Notes: Stylized eye detail is indicated on some zoomorphic pestles. There is also an eye detail on a bird statuette.

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)
– Yes
Notes: Stylized anthropomorphic decorations are seen on several bone objects and a few stone vessel fragments. Moreover, a human sculpture illustrates anthropomorphic features.

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)
– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife
– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– No

↳ Humans

– Yes

Notes: On the stone vessels and other stone objects (i.e. symbolic objects, grooved stones) were identified decorated stylized human figures.

↳ Supernatural narratives

– No

↳ Human narratives

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

–Percentage: 30

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

–Square meters: 80

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

–Height, meters: 2

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

–Square meters: 70

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

–Height, meters: 3

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Sand

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Grass

– Field doesn't know

↳ Stone
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: There have been found ground stone tools in the wall of the buildings as the building material.

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:
– No

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:
– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:
– Field doesn't know

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:
– Percentage: 30

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:
Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.
– Square meters: 80

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 2

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 70

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 3

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Sand

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳

Is this material sourced locally:

– Field doesn't know

↳

Grass

– Field doesn't know

↳

Stone

– Yes

↳

Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: There have been found ground stone tools in the wall of the buildings as the building material.

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳

Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳

On the inside:

– Yes

Notes: On two of the walls of stone pillars situated in the center of the structure were found red plaster partially. As the plaster partly survived, it is obscure if there were any decorative elements on them.

↳

Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

↳

Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

↳ Statues of humans:

– Yes

Notes: A human statue of approximately 38,5 cm in height inside Public Building 15 is associated with the ancestor cult (Schmandt-Besserrat, 2013: 329).

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

Notes: The human face was carved in relief on the 2 altars in Public Building 15.

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– No

↳ Other type of decoration:

– Yes [specify]: On the floor of one of the Public Building was found terrazzo floor.

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– Yes

Notes: Stylized eye detail is indicated on some zoomorphic pestles.

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: Stylized eye detail is indicated on some zoomorphic pestles. There is also an eye detail on a bird statuette.

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: Stylized anthropomorphic decorations are seen on several bone objects and a few stone vessel fragments. Moreover, a human sculpture illustrates anthropomorphic features.

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– No

↳ Humans

– Yes

Notes: On the stone vessels and other stone objects (i.e. symbolic objects, grooved stones) were identified decorated stylized human figures.

↳ Supernatural narratives

– No

↳ Human narratives

– No

Beliefs and Practices

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Field doesn't know

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is divination present:

– Field doesn't know

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: In one of the public buildings, there is a seating area (70x17 cm) where 26 people can sit on a bench in front of the enclosure wall.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there synchronic practices:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:
– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is not known for the time being as chemical studies are still under study.

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The presence of a significant amount of animal bone in one of the public buildings is related to butchery activities. It does not mean that there happened sacrificial activities in the building.

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Although chemical studies are still ongoing, the very small pestles may have been used to smash some healing plants.

Are previously human spirits present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Since the only argument is the presence of mortuary practices, we can argue about previous human spirits.

Are festivals present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The presence of nearly 1500 animal bones (such as pigs, deer, sheep, goats, cattle, mammals, rodents and dogs) in Public Building 8 suggests that feasting activities might have been held in this area.

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Field doesn't know

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Field doesn't know

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– Field doesn't know

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

Notes: Only a few stone beads, bone tools, and symbolic stone objects were found.

↳ Valuable/precious items:

– Yes

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Since stone symbolic objects are associated with belief system, these items can be evaluated as valuable objects.

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The presence of stylized symbolic objects in some graves at the site may indicate some form of spiritual contact with supernatural non-human agents.

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Yes

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

Notes: There are various stages of renovation on both the walls and floors of public buildings, although it is not known if they were renewed periodically.

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Field doesn't know

Are formal burials present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Since there is only one human statue in the settlement, it is not possible to say that it specifically

points to a god. However, it is known from contemporary examples that it points to a belief such as the cult of ancestors, not a single great god.

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– Field doesn't know

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Personal effects:

– Yes

Notes: Only a few stone beads, bone tools, and symbolic stone objects were found.

Valuable/precious items:

– Yes

Other

– Other [specify]: Since stone symbolic objects are associated with belief system, these items can be evaluated as valuable objects.

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Since the only argument is the presence of mortuary practices, we can argue about previous human spirits.

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The presence of stylized symbolic objects in some graves at the site may indicate some form of spiritual contact with supernatural non-human agents.

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Since there is only one human statue in the settlement, it is not possible to say that it specifically points to a god. However, it is known from contemporary examples that it points to a belief such as the cult of ancestors, not a single great god.

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Field doesn't know

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: In one of the public buildings, there is a seating area (70x17 cm) where 26 people can sit on a bench in front of the enclosure wall.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is not known for the time being as chemical studies are still under study.

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The presence of a significant amount of animal bone in one of the public buildings is related to butchery activities. It does not mean that there happened sacrificial activities in the building.

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Field doesn't know

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Field doesn't know

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

Is it required:

– Field doesn't know

Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Yes

Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

Notes: There are various stages of renovation on both the walls and floors of public buildings, although it is not known if they were renewed periodically.

Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Field doesn't know

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The presence of nearly 1500 animal bones (such as pigs, deer, sheep, goats, cattle, mammals,

rodents and dogs) in Public Building 8 suggests that feasting activities might have been held in this area.

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– Field doesn't know

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Although chemical studies are still ongoing, the very small pestles may have been used to smash some healing plants.

Institutions and Scriptures

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Field doesn't know

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: In the northern operation of the site, three neighborhoods were identified that are connected to at least three different public buildings. On the other hand, public buildings display a more complex image, especially when considering their interior arrangements. One of the public buildings may have been used for the production of chipped tools. However, public buildings primarily served the community in a religious sense.

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: No data on religious specialists could be found in the rectangular planned structures.

Nevertheless, we do not know whether such a structure belonging to a religious specialist or specialists existed in the unexcavated area.

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The groups that built the stone monuments at Gre Filla were hunter-gatherers. Although the control of goods is managed within the framework of a certain system in agricultural societies, there is no systematic control over resources in hunter-gatherer Neolithic groups.

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– No

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Field doesn't know

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: No data on religious specialists could be found in the rectangular planned structures.

Nevertheless, we do not know whether such a structure belonging to a religious specialist or specialists existed in the unexcavated area.

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– No

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The groups that built the stone monuments at Gre Filla were hunter-gatherers. Although the control of goods is managed within the framework of a certain system in agricultural societies, there is no systematic control over resources in hunter-gatherer Neolithic groups.

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: In the northern operation of the site, three neighborhoods were identified that are connected to at least three different public buildings. On the other hand, public buildings display a more complex image, especially when considering their interior arrangements. One of the public buildings may have been used for the production of chipped tools. However, public buildings primarily served the community in a religious sense.

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Pre-Pottery Neolithic Gre Filla, Ökse, A. Tuba. "Yukarı Dicle Havzası-ambar Çayı Vadisi Yerleşim Tarihi". *Olba* 28 (2020): 1-34.

Reference: Pre-Pottery Neolithic Gre Filla, Akkermans, Peter M. M. G. , and Glenn M. Schwartz. *The Archaeology of Syria, from Complex Hunter Gatherers to Early Urban Societies (ca. 16.000-300 B.C.)*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2003.

Reference: Pre-Pottery Neolithic Gre Filla, Çelik, Bahattin. "Şanlıurfa İli Yüzey Araştırması, 2018", no. 40 (December 20, 2018). <https://doi.org/10.17498/kdeniz.453054>.

Reference: Pre-Pottery Neolithic Gre Filla, Dietrich, O., and J. Notroff. "A Sanctuary, or so Fair a House? in Defense of an Archaeology of Cult at Pre-pottery Neolithic Göbekli Tepe". In *Defining the Sacred: Approaches to the Archaeology of Religion in the Near East*, edited by N. Laneri, 75–89. Oxford: Oxbow Books, 2015.

Reference: Pre-Pottery Neolithic Gre Filla, Karul, Necmi. "The Beginning of the Neolithic in Southeast Anatolia". *Documenta Praehistorica* 47 (December 1, 2020): 76–95. <https://doi.org/10.4312/dp.47.5>.

Reference: Pre-Pottery Neolithic Gre Filla, Kabukcu, Ceren, Eleni Asouti, Nadja Pöllath, Joris Peters, and Necmi Karul. "Pathways to Plant Domestication in Southeast Anatolia Based on New Data from Aceramic Neolithic Gusir Höyük". *Scientific Reports* 11 (January 22, 2021): 2112. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-81757-9>.

Reference: Pre-Pottery Neolithic Gre Filla, Aurenche, Olivier. "“altın Üçgen” Ve Önasya’da Neolitik’in Başlangıcı". In *12.000 Yıl Önce Anadolu İnsanlığın En Eski Anıtları* (p. 419-429), edited by C. Litcher and S. Gün. Stuttgart: Verlagsbüro Wais & Partner, 2007.

Reference: Pre-Pottery Neolithic Gre Filla, Hodder, Ian, and Scott Hutson. *Reading the Past: Current Approaches to Interpretation in Archaeology*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2013.

Reference: Pre-Pottery Neolithic Gre Filla, Erim Özdoğan, Aslı, and Neziha Başgelen. "Çayönü". In *Anadolu’da Uygarlığın Doğuşu Ve Avrupa’ya Yayılımı. Türkiye’de Neolitik Dönem: Yeni Kazılar, Yeni Bulgular* (metinler), edited by Mehmet Özdoğan. İstanbul: Arkeoloji ve Sanat Yayınları, 2007.

Reference: Pre-Pottery Neolithic Gre Filla, Erim Özdoğan, Aslı, and Savaş Sarılaltun. "Sumaki Höyük Batman/beşiri". In *Batman Müzesi İlisu Barajı Kurtarma Kazıları*, edited by F. Baş. Batman: Fikirzen Ajans Reklamcılık, 2018.

Reference: Pre-Pottery Neolithic Gre Filla, Goring-Morris, A. Nigel, and Anna Belfer-Cohen. "The Southern Levant (cisjordan) During the Neolithic Period (p. 147-169)". In *The Oxford Handbook of the Archaeology of the Levant: C. 8000-332 BCE*, edited by Ann E. Killebrew and Margreet Steiner. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2014.

Reference: Pre-Pottery Neolithic Gre Filla, Karadoğan, Sabri, and Gülriiz Kozbe. "Yukarı Dicle Havzasının (batman - Bismil Arası) Jeomorfolojik Özellikleri Ve Arkeolojik Yerleşme/buluntu Yerlerinin Dönemler Boyunca Mekan Etkileşimleri (p. 540-564)". In *Profesör Doktor İlhan Kayan'a Armağan*, edited by E. Öner. Bornova: Ege Üniversitesi Yayınları-Edebiyat Fakültesi Yayın NO: 181, 2013.

Reference: Pre-Pottery Neolithic Gre Filla, Kartal, Metin, and Harun Taşkiran. "Yontmataş Bulguları Işığında Yukarı Dicle Havzası’nda Yeni Bir Neolitik Yerleşim: Boncuklu Tarla". *Ankara Üniversitesi Dil Ve Tarih-coğrafya Fakültesi Dergisi* 54, no. 1 (2014): 481–92. https://doi.org/10.1501/dtcfder_0000001392.

Reference: Pre-Pottery Neolithic Gre Filla, Invalid csl-json to parse. Error: "'NoneType' object has no attribute 'group'"

Reference: Pre-Pottery Neolithic Gre Filla, Konak, Ayşin. "Gre Filla Çanak Çömleksiz Neolitik Dönem Yerleşiminden Kesici Kenarlı Sürtme Taş Aletler". *Akademik İncelemeler Dergisi* 17, no. 1 (April 15, 2022): 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.17550/akademikincelemeler.1018603>.

Reference: Pre-Pottery Neolithic Gre Filla, Kuijt, Ian. "The Regeneration of Life". *Current Anthropology* 49, no. 2 (April 2008): 171–98. <https://doi.org/10.1086/526097>.

Reference: Pre-Pottery Neolithic Gre Filla, Kuijt, Ian, and Adrian Nigel Gorin-Morris. "Foraging, Farming,

and Social Complexity in the Pre-pottery Neolithic of the Southern Levant: A Review and Synthesis". *Journal of World Prehistory* 16, no. 4 (2002): 361-440. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1022973114090>.

Reference: Pre-Pottery Neolithic Gre Filla, Lubbock, John. *Prehistoric Times: As Illustrated by Ancient Remains and the Manners and Customs of Modern Savages*. London: Williams and Norgate, 1865.

Reference: Pre-Pottery Neolithic Gre Filla, Miyake, Yutaka, Osuma Maeda, Kenichi Tanno, Hitomi Hongo, and Can Y. Gündem. "New Excavations at Hasankeyf Höyük: A 10th Millennium Cal. BC Site on the Upper Tigris, Southeast Anatolia". *Neo-lithics* 1, no. 12 (2012): 3-7.

Reference: Pre-Pottery Neolithic Gre Filla, Moore, Andrew M. T.. "A Four-stage Sequence for the Levantine Neolithic, Ca. 8500-3750 B. C.". *Bulletin of the American Society of Overseas Research* 246 (April 1982). <https://doi.org/10.2307/1356585>.

Reference: Pre-Pottery Neolithic Gre Filla, Moore, A.M.T., G.C. Hillman, and A.J. Legge. *Village on the Euphrates. From Foraging to Farming at Abu Hureyra*. Oxford University Press, 2000.

Reference: Pre-Pottery Neolithic Gre Filla, Muşkara, Üftade, and Aysin Konak. "Obsidian Source Identification at Gre Filla, Turkey". *Journal of Archaeological Science: Reports* 38 (August 2021): 103003. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jasrep.2021.103003>.

Reference: Pre-Pottery Neolithic Gre Filla, Muşkara, Üftade, and Mahmut Aydın. "Elemental Analysis of Pre-pottery Neolithic B Copper Finds from Gre Filla". *Mediterranean Archaeology and Archaeometry* 22, no. 1 (2022): 1-14. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5906704>.

Reference: Pre-Pottery Neolithic Gre Filla, Ökse, A. Tuba, Aysin Konak, and Vehbi Yurt. "Ambar Barajı - Ambar Höyük, Gre Filla (ambar I) Ve Kendale Hecala 2018 Kazısı (p. 299-313)". In 41. Kazı Sonuçları Toplantısı (1), edited by Adil Özme. Ankara: Kültür ve Turizm Bakanlığı, 2020.

Reference: Pre-Pottery Neolithic Gre Filla, Ökse, A. Tuba. "Yukarı Dicle Havzasında Yeni Keşfedilen Neolitik Çağ Höyükleri (p. 28-31)". *Aktüel Arkeoloji*, 73, 2020.

Reference: Pre-Pottery Neolithic Gre Filla, Ökse, A. Tuba. "New Data on the Late Neolithic Pottery from the Northern Upper Tigris Region: Ambar Dam Reservoir (p. 307-322)". In *Neolithic Pottery from the Near East Third International Workshop on Ceramics from the Late Neolithic Near East 7-9 March, 2019 - Antalya PROCEEDINGS*, edited by Rana Özbal, Mücella Erdalkıran, and Yukiko Tonoike. İstanbul: AKMED, 2021.

Reference: Pre-Pottery Neolithic Gre Filla, Ökse, A. Tuba. "Ambar Dam Salvage Excavations in 2018-2020: Ambar Höyük, Gre Filla and Kendale Hecala (p. 4-20)". In *Archaeology of Anatolia Volume IV: Recent Discoveries (2019-2020)*, edited by Sharon R. Steadman and Gregory McMahon. Newcastle upon Tyne: Cambridge Scholar Press, 2021.

Reference: Pre-Pottery Neolithic Gre Filla, Ökse, A. Tuba. "Gre Filla: Yukarı Dicle Havzasında Ambar Çayı Kenarına Kurulmuş Bir Çanak Çömlek Öncesi Neolitik Dönem Yerleşimi". *Arkeoloji Ve Sanat* 169 (2022): 25-46.

Reference: Pre-Pottery Neolithic Gre Filla, Ökse, A. Tuba, Vehbi Yurt, Aysin Konak, Mesut Vural, and İ. Tayfur Aşkar. "Ambar Barajı- Ambar Höyük Ve Gre Filla (ambar I) 2019-2020 Kazıları". In *2019-2020 Yılı Kazı Çalışmaları*, 1, edited by Adil Özme, 231-48. Ankara: Kültür ve Turizm Bakanlığı Yayınları, 2022.

Reference: Pre-Pottery Neolithic Gre Filla, Özbaşaran, Mihriban, and Miquel Molist. "Akarçay Tepe 2005". *Anatolia Antiqua* 14, no. 1 (2006): 245-49. <https://doi.org/10.3406/anata.2006.1077>.

Reference: Pre-Pottery Neolithic Gre Filla, Özdoğan, Mehmet. "Mezraa-teleilat". In *The Neolithic in Turkey New Excavations & New Research (the Euphrates Basin)* (p. 203-260), edited by Mehmet Özdoğan and Nezih Başgelen. İstanbul: Arkeoloji ve Sanat Yayınları, 2011.

Reference: Pre-Pottery Neolithic Gre Filla, Özkaya, Vechi , and Oya San. "Körtik Tepe Bulgular Işığında Kültürel Doku Üzerine İlk Gözlemler". In *Anadolu'da Uygarlığın Doğuşu Ve Avrupa'ya Yayılımı. Türkiye'de Neolitik Dönem: Yeni Kazılar, Yeni Bulgular (metinler)* (p. 21-36), edited by Mehmet Özdoğan and Nezih Başgelen. İstanbul: Arkeoloji ve Sanat Yayınları, 2007.

Reference: Pre-Pottery Neolithic Gre Filla, Peasnell, Brian. "2002 Diyarbakır Small Streams Archaeological Survey". In *Kazı Sonuçları Toplantısı (21: 2)* (p. 29-44). Ankara: Kültür ve Turizm Bakanlığı, 2004.

Reference: Pre-Pottery Neolithic Gre Filla, Renfrew, Colin, and Paul Bahn. *Archaeology: Theories, Methods and Practice*. London: Thames & Hudson, 1991.

Reference: Pre-Pottery Neolithic Gre Filla, Rosenberg, Michael. "Hallan Çemi". In *Anadolu'da Uygarlığın Doğuşu Ve Avrupa'ya Yayılımı. Türkiye'de Neolitik Dönem: Yeni Kazılar, Yeni Bulgular (metinler)* (p. 1-11), edited by Mehmet Özdoğan and Nezih Başgelen. İstanbul: Arkeoloji ve Sanat Yayınları, 2007.

Reference: Pre-Pottery Neolithic Gre Filla, Uluçam, Abduselam, and Yutaka Miyake. "Hasankeyf Höyük Kazısı". In *Batman Müzesi İlisu Barajı Kurtarma Kazıları* (p. 25-54), edited by F. Baş. Batman: Fikirzen Ajans Reklamcılık, 2018.

Reference: Pre-Pottery Neolithic Gre Filla, Verhoeven, Marc. "Transformations of Society : The Changing Role of Ritual and Symbolism in the PPNB and the PN in the Levant, Syria and South-east Anatolia" 28, no. 1 (2002). <https://doi.org/10.3406/paleo.2002.4735>.

Reference: Pre-Pottery Neolithic Gre Filla, Vita-Finzi, C., E. S. Higgs, D. Sturdy, J. Harriss, A. J. Legge, and H. Tippet. "Prehistoric Economy in the Mount Carmel Area of Palestine: Site Catchment Analysis". *Proceedings of the Prehistoric Society* 36 (December 1970): 1-37. <https://doi.org/10.1017/s0079497x00013074>.

Reference: Pre-Pottery Neolithic Gre Filla, Voigt, Mary M. . "Excavations at Neolithic Gritille". *Anatolica XV* (1988): 215-32.

Reference: Pre-Pottery Neolithic Gre Filla, Tekin, Halil. *Tarihöncesinde Mezopotamya: Yeni Yaklaşımlar, Yeni Yorumlar Ve Yeni Kronoloji*. Ankara: Bilgin Kültür ve Sanat Yayınları, 2017.

Reference: Pre-Pottery Neolithic Gre Filla, Stordeur, Danielle, and Frédéric Abbès. "Du PPNA Au PPNB : Mise En Lumière D'une Phase De Transition À Jerf El Ahmar (syrie)" 99, no. 3 (2002): 563-95. <https://doi.org/10.3406/bspf.2002.12712>.

Reference: Pre-Pottery Neolithic Gre Filla, Hours, Francis, Olivier Aurenche, Jacques Cauvin, Marie-Claire Cauvin, Lorraine Copeland, and Paul Sanlaville. *Atlas Des Sites Du Proche Orient (14000-5700 BP)*. Maison de l'Orient Méditerranéen, 1994.